

Field Guides

GUIDE FOR GRADUATE SCHOOL APPLICATIONS

Hints and tips for the PhD application process.

So you are interested in applying to graduate school - congrats you've taken the first big step! Applying to PhD programs is different from applying to college and often requires you to connect with programs and specific faculty before applying. This may seem overwhelming, but hang in there - we are here to help!

We have compiled this cheat sheet containing tips and suggestions from the experiences of current graduate students. The suggested timeline/tips will be centered around PhD programs in ecology, evolution, and related fields - but hopefully can be used as a general reference for other programs you may be interested in.

Disclaimer: This is definitely not the only way to apply to graduate programs - each application and applicant are unique! Move at your own pace - there is no one "right" way to apply!

This guide was compiled by the Field Guides Mentoring Program at the University of Minnesota - Twin Cities. We are a graduate student run mentoring group focused on increasing diversity and representation in ecology and adjacent fields. Explore more of our work and access additional resources on our [website](#).

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TIMELINE & CHECKLIST

Most PhD applications will be due in mid-December. Below we have outlined a suggested timeline starting the summer one-year before your program would begin. Tasks are loosely organized by season but again, there is no one correct way to apply - move at your own pace!

For more detailed information on each task, see the following pages in this document. Questions on terminology? Check out [the glossary](#) at the end of this document.

SUMMER

May - August

- Reflect on what you'd like to study
- Research graduate programs
- Identify potential advisors
- Gain research experience/network

FALL

August - October

- Organize your CV
- Study/take the TOEFL (international students only)
- Study/take the GRE (if needed)
- Contact potential advisors
- Contact potential letter of recommendation writers (4+)
- Begin application statements
- Apply for fellowship opportunities

LATE FALL & WINTER

October - December

- Meet with potential advisors/lab members
- Submit fellowship applications
- Finalize written statements
- Submit program applications

SPRING

February - April

- Interview
- Check in with potential advisors
- Select final program

WHY GRAD SCHOOL?

If you know, you know... but there is no need to rush into graduate programs - often people take some time off to gain relevant experience and take an academic break before jumping into a PhD program. Spend some time thinking about what is best for you and where you are at in life.

Some good questions to ask yourself:

Is a PhD required for the jobs I am interested in?

Do I like the field of study enough to devote 5- 6 years of my focus?

Am I burned out academically? Would I benefit from some time off?

- You do not need to go directly from your bachelors into a Masters or PhD!
- Many (paid) jobs are available in research and will allow you to spend some time gaining experience and exploring potential interests.
- Technician jobs are a great way to gain experience and technical skills while having some time to recover from school. Technician positions can be found in university labs, in industry research, and in government agencies!
- Others spend some time in careers completely separate from academia: consulting and non-profit work often support recent graduates. These jobs are a good way to explore more 9-5, office based science jobs - Do you miss working in the field/at the bench?

Do I have enough experience to be successful starting grad-school? Have I spent enough time involved in research to know that I enjoy it?

- Research experience matters - you should have spent some time in a research environment before applying to PhD programs. This not only will help you get into schools but will help you narrow your potential research interests.
- A master degree can help to gain focused experience with the independent research process, but definitely not required before a PhD.
- Some time spent working in the research space can help you gain experience and hone your interests. Though you may feel like gap-years are prolonging your time in school, often coming into a program with developed skills and research questions can help you move through the program quicker.

Consider your mental health:

Grad school is a challenge. We often prepare for the intellectual challenges we will face but you should also consider the psychological ones. Imposter syndrome, anxiety, and stress will likely play a role in your PhD pursuits. How well do you manage stress? Are you feeling burnt out? Do you have support systems in place? Tip: Check out what mental health services are offered through your potential programs!

TIMELINE WITH TIPS & HINTS

Questions on terminology? Check out [the glossary](#) at the end of this document.

SUMMER

May - August

Reflect on what you are interested in studying:

- What are you passionate about?
Tip: This does NOT need to be the same topic you studied in undergrad
- What research/academic questions intrigue you?
- It's okay to have diverse interests, each program or advisor you are interested in can research something completely different!

Research graduate programs:

Look for...

- Potential faculty that interest you.
- Programs that do work in an area of science that interest you.
Tip: Ask around - see if your professors, TAs, or mentors have any suggestions!
- Strong department (see box 1)

Other things to consider (don't just go off school name/reputation):

- Location: You will be living here for 5-6 years! What are your hobbies and interests outside of school? Do you like small towns? Major cities? Close to nature? What climate do you prefer?
- Life/Support Systems: Do you want to live closer to family/friends? A partner? Is there transportation in place to make travel easy?

Identify potential advisors:

You'll want to identify some labs that you are excited to work in. Unlike undergrad, you will need to contact potential advisors a few months BEFORE you submit your applications (it is a requirement). Start with a large list that you can narrow down as you go through the application process (aim for 10-20 to start, whittle down to 4-6).

To identify advisors of interest you can...

- Find/review papers you've read and liked, or work you think is really cool. Make sure you have read 4-5 of their lab's papers (sometimes an author will publish a paper on a topic that may not be the focus of their lab/research!)

- Look through faculty lists on the website of programs you are interested in.
- Ask professors, mentors, teachers, TAs, etc... if they know of any opportunities or if they have recommendations for people to contact .

Tip: if you are interested in ecology - try subscribing to ECOLOG-L. An online forum where faculty can post PhD openings. Find instructions for logging in [here](#).

- Scroll twitter! Scientists love twitter and many openings for graduate students are posted (and re-tweeted) online - [here](#) is an example! Consider making yourself a professional/scientific twitter and start following people you are interested in to keep an eye out for opportunities.
- Check out faculty status (try their website, recent publications, or twitter) Are they looking for students? Do they appear to be active?

Tip: Positions do not need to be advertised to be available - it never hurts to ask!

Gain research experience & network:

Try to engage with science this summer! Think about applying to [work in a lab](#) part time, or join a research focus internship like the [National Science Foundation](#) “REU” (Research Experience for Undergrads) program. If you can’t work in a lab or have other commitments, here are some other options to consider:

- Attend a scientific conference - even if you do not present any research, they are super great places for networking and often your school/university or the conference itself have [funds to send students](#). Ask around!
 - ESA (the Ecological Society of America) and ‘Evolution’ conferences are great meetings for EEB-focused undergrads
 - SACNAS (Society Advancing Chicanos/Hispanics & Native Americans in Science) hosts a [National Diversity in STEM](#) conference - an undergrad-focused event where many grad-student openings are advertised along with professional development opportunities.
- Ask to sit-in on lab meetings of a research group that interests you
- Ask a professor, TA, or mentor (think someone who might write you a letter of recommendation) to get coffee and discuss grad-school
- Volunteer with a science-outreach organization (example: [Market Science](#))
- Attend a seminar or workshop about applying to graduate school. Keep an eye on your school’s career center!

Box 1: What Makes A Strong Graduate Program?

- **Breadth of Research Programs:**
 - You will be working with other faculty members outside of your advisor (collaborations, classes, and committees) Look for programs with multiple faculty/labs that interest you.
- **Facilities:**
 - Do they have the facilities and equipment to support the research you are interested in? Think field stations, supercomputers, museum collections, etc...
- **Funding Availability:**
 - PhD students **should be funded for at least 5 years**. At a minimum, “funding” means the department covers your tuition and health care, and pays you a living stipend. This may require you to teach or work as a research assistant, but you should be **guaranteed** funding. If not, we **highly** suggest looking at other programs. You should not need to take out loans to complete a PhD (note: this is not true of masters programs).
 - What is the average student living stipend? You may need to wait until you visit to get a specific number - but you should be able to find a range [online](#). You can also always email the program and ask!
 - Tip:** this should scale with the [cost of living](#) wherever the program is located. Living stipends vary widely from program to program (\$13,000 - \$50,000 annually). Be reflective and critical here - does this amount seem like enough to support your needs/desired lifestyle (ie living alone vs with roommates?)
- **Time to Degree:**
 - How quickly do students finish the program? (note the average is 5-6 years)
 - What types of careers do recent graduates go into?
- **Advisor Selection:**
 - Lab rotations vs direct lab assignments (find this on the program website):
 - Some programs have you rotate (4-6 weeks) in 3-4 labs your first year of graduate school before selecting your final advisor. Other programs you select your advisor(s) in your application.
 - Rotations can be helpful if you are interested in multiple faculty at a school or aren't 100% sure which topic you want to focus on, but can extend your time in the program.
 - If the program does not have rotations you **must** be in contact with a potential advisor BEFORE submitting your application. (see box 2).
- **Demographics:**
 - Age, gender, race, ethnicity distributions in the graduate students and the faculty are important to consider. Also consider the demographics of the city of the college/university.

FALL

August - October

Organize your CV:

A curriculum vitae (CV) is a latin phrase that means “course of life”. A CV is an academic resume and by the name, you might guess that it should be more detailed than a typical resume! In contrast to a resume where we are focused on showing only the top 2-3 most important experiences, a CV highlights *all* of your major experiences and can (& should) be more than one page..

- The goal of your CV should be to highlight your research-related experiences. Beginning post-high school, include any academic/research/science activity you can. A good overview and some examples can be found [here](#) & [here](#).
 - Focus on highlighting your relevant academic experience first (in reverse chronological order - newest first!)
 - Break your experiences into sections: common sections include: Education, Teaching Experiences, Research Experiences, Publications, Presentations, Awards/Honors, Outreach, Relevant Coursework, Lab Skills, and more.
 - Feel free to include a small section of non-academic things that may make you a unique/strong candidate (“Leadership” or “Service” can be strong section titles). For example: captain of a university sports team or club president may not be academic but can show you have both leadership and time management skills.

Tip: your school’s career or writing centers can edit a CV for you! After you have developed a draft make an appointment! Also think about sending your draft around to other mentors, friends, and professors for feedback!

Take the TOEFL (international students only):

The TOEFL or “Test Of English as a Foreign Language” is a test of English proficiency in reading, listening, speaking, and writing. Often the TOEFL is a requirement for international students applying to programs in the United States.

- Often students who received an undergraduate degree (or attended one full academic year) at an accredited United States university are exempt from the requirement. Be sure to check each of your program websites for specific requirements and eligibility.
- Practice tests can be found [here](#)

Study and take the GRE (only if needed):

The GRE (Graduate Record Exam) is a standardized test that has historically been an admissions requirement for many graduate schools (think SAT/ACT of grad-school). However, many schools are dropping their GRE requirement -- be sure to check program websites to see if it is required for your programs of interest. Send an email to the program to clarify if their website is not clear.

- You do not need to spend time and money on this exam if it is not required - it will not help your admission (even if it is listed as "optional"). Instead, focus on the other aspects of your application (connection with potential advisors, research experience, letters of recommendation, written statements, etc..) which hold a lot more weight in your application and admission.

Tip: It is good to check potential fellowship requirements as well - some may ask for GRE scores.

- If you do need to take it - don't stress. Spend ~ 1-2 month studying (not full time). Ecology/Life science programs typically do not place a ton of weight on GRE scores.
 - There are many free study resources/practice tests online (www.gre.org) and on our [Field Guide Website](#). Your local/college library likely has GRE study books you can check out instead of buying - or try facebook marketplace/ebay! Don't worry about getting the newest version of the study materials.
 - The test can get expensive (~ \$200+ registration). If finances are tight, look into fee waivers [here](#) - start this early if you can!
- If you don't get the score you want: don't be discouraged (the GRE has a terrible track record of [predicting grad-student success](#)). Still apply even if you do not hit the score range listed on the website.

Contact potential advisors/faculty members:

When searching for graduate programs, you will need to contact potential advisors (faculty members you [researched earlier](#)) in the months prior to submitting your application. Though some program websites might say reaching out to faculty is 'recommended' - it is, in most cases, a requirement. As many life science applications are due in December, you should plan to reach out sometime August-early October.

- Reach out with an email - keep it short and directed (see box 2). Be sure to check their lab website to see if they have any instructions - some have specific forms, others will ask for transcripts/CVs, or request particular subject lines!
- Don't be discouraged if you do not hear back immediately (this is why it is good to reach out early!) If you haven't heard back in 2 weeks, send a follow up.
 - Avoid sending emails close to the start of the semester/quarter
- If they respond and are not taking students, it is fair to ask if they know of any other opportunities or faculty that may be a good match!

Box 2: Nail the Introductory Email

When reaching out to potential advisors - be sure to individually tailor each email to the lab and professor. Though they can all follow a similar structure, make sure they are specific to each lab's research (ie the red section below!!). Faculty can usually tell when you are sending a mass-email (which is not very personable and will often result in your email being ignored).

General outline:

1. **Introduction:** name, major/degree, university, and future goal/timeline (masters, PhD, etc...)
Tip: ALWAYS address potential advisors as Dr.
2. **Overview of your research interest:** what have you done in the past, what do you want to study in the future (keep this very, very short!)
Tip: Avoid fillers like "I am highly motivated" or "I am committed to academic excellence" etc...
3. **Why do you think this specific lab is a good fit/why you are excited about their specific work/projects** (this should be the bulk of the email!)
Tip: you should always read through a handful of their papers before reaching out!
4. **Ask if you can chat** over the phone/zoom to learn more.

Example introduction email:

Dear Dr. Potential-advisor,

My name is Excited Student. I am a senior at the University of Minnesota graduating with a BS in ecology this spring and looking to begin in a PhD program in the fall of 2023. I have spent the past two years working in the lab of Dr. Biologist on a project relating light dynamics in tropical forests to nitrogen-fixing bacteria and just returned from a 3-month field season in Brazil collecting data for my senior thesis. I am broadly interested in studying ecosystem response to changing climates through the lens of the microbial community.

I recently read your lab's paper on the effects of drought on nitrogen-fixing bacteria communities in the rainforests of Costa Rica. I think your lab's work on the effects of weather and climate on microbiomes is fascinating and aligns well with my own research interests. In grad school, I'd like to apply my research to forest conservation and work at this intersection of policy and science - so I am also very interested in your lab's involvement in conservation and climate policy.

I am really interested in learning more about your lab and any potential graduate student opportunities that may be available. Are you available to talk by phone or zoom sometime in the next few weeks? I am generally available Mondays, Thursdays, and Fridays from 1-4:30pm CDT*. I have attached a copy of my CV below. Please let me know if you would like any other information.

Respectfully,

Excited Student

* Propose some days of the week/times that work for you - faculty will appreciate this! Be sure to note your time zone if you are reaching out to faculty around the country.

Ask potential letter writers:

Identify and contact 4 potential references (most programs will ask for 3). Ideally letters should be from researchers who you have worked with, advisors, or faculty you have taken multiple courses with.

- Choose letter-writers that know you well! They should be able to comment on your work ethic, creative thinking, drive, and any other attributes. Often faculty will consult with postdocs/graduate students you have worked closely with.
 - Strive to have as many strong faculty-written letters as possible, but make sure at least one letter is from a professor or research scientist. Even if you work mostly with a graduate student, always ask the professor in charge of the lab!
- Faculty may receive requests from multiple students, particularly as deadlines near. Try to plan ahead and give your letter writer at least a month to write you a good letter.

Tip: If you are asking for several letters from someone, it can be helpful to send them a spreadsheet with information about each request, such as the deadline, how to submit the letter, and anything you want them to emphasize.
- Provide your letter writers with additional material as needed. If your letter writer is not your primary advisor, it can be helpful to send them a copy of your CV when you request a letter of recommendation. This will provide context of your other accomplishments that they can expand on in their letter.

Begin application written statements:

Programs will differ widely in how they handle applications, however most programs will require 2-3 written statements: personal, research, and diversity. Check each program website carefully for specific requirements.

- Though each statement will need to be personalized to the school and advisor, you can usually use the same general essay for each application.
- Make it extremely clear that you have talked with a potential advisor (and name them!)
- Start as early as you can so you have time to get feedback from your mentors, the writing center on campus, your advisor/career center, your friends, your family, your potential advisor, , , anyone!
 - Sharing writing can sometimes feel cringy or embarrassing - but these statements are always a little cheesy and it will benefit you to get as many eyes on them as possible (especially those who aren't in science).

Apply for fellowships (optional):

Fellowships provide you (as an individual) with funding to cover your tuition and living expenses. Fellowships are particularly useful when applying for grad school as you are coming in with money rather than the department or your advisor needing to support you. Typically students not on fellowship will work as a teaching assistant (TA) or research assistant (RA) for 20 hrs/wk for the department to cover their tuition and living stipend.

Why apply to optional fellowships?

- Increases program acceptance rate (admittance not dependant on department funding)
- Higher living stipend (at some schools)
- You can focus on research! Funding without teaching or other responsibilities gives you a lot more time to devote towards your research. This can help you move through your program faster and allows flexibility during the semester to travel or do field work.

Fellowship applications often require personal and research statements and letters of recommendation (like mini-grad school apps!) Be sure to give yourself a lot of time to tackle all of these! Consider consulting with your current or potential future research advisor for help writing and developing these statements as they are often extremely competitive.

See box 3 for suggest fellowships in ecology/evolution

Box 3: Potential Funding Sources & Fellowships for EEB

1. NSF GRFP (3 years of support) - due mid-October
 - <https://www.nsfgrfp.org/>
 - US citizens
2. Soros Fellowship for New Americans (3 years of support)- due late-October
 - <https://www.pdsoros.org/apply>
 - For US immigrants or children of immigrants that are US or naturalized citizens, green card holders , refugee/asylees, or attended highschool & college in US
3. Fulbright Fellowship (1 year support abroad) - due mid-October
 - <https://us.fulbrightonline.org/about/types-of-awards/study-research>
 - International Students or US student going abroad
4. Ford Fellowship (3 years of support) - due: early December
 - <https://sites.nationalacademies.org/PGA/FordFellowships/index.htm>
 - Focused on increasing/supporting ethnic and racial diversity
 - US Citizens
5. The Hertz Fellowship (5 years of support) - due: late-October
 - <https://www.hertzfoundation.org/the-fellowship/apply-for-fellowship/>
 - US Citizens

LATE FALL & WINTER

October - December

Meet with potential advisors

Set up a short introduction meeting/zoom call with each advisor you are considering submitting an application with. Be sure to set this meeting up well in advance of application due dates - many advisors will want to chat with you more than once prior to submission of your application.

- Prepare! Look through their website, google scholar, and read a few of their papers (4-5). You do not need to memorize them, but have a good idea of what they study. It can help to write the major points down and have them in front of you during the call.
- Come with questions (and answers). Bring questions to ask (see box 4) and think through answers to questions you may be asked about your research and interests.
- Take notes! Especially if you are meeting with multiple potential advisors!
- Always follow up quickly with a thank-you email. Thank them for their time and if you are interested in the lab, ask if you can chat with one of their current graduate students or post-docs (a research role many people take right after they get their PhD).
 - They should say yes, enthusiastically. If they say no or repeatedly avoid your question - that is a major red flag!

Box 4: I have a zoom meeting - now what?

Good questions/topics to discuss in a meeting with a potential advisor

Topics to discuss:

- Talk about what research you have done and what projects you have worked on. Try to relate these experiences to the work being done in this lab.
- Share what research you are excited about doing in the future. Talk through some research ideas or cool projects
- Walk through your long-term career goals: do you want to work as a professor? In research? In industry?
- Faculty love to talk about their work - ask them questions about their current project/recent papers (usually they will do most of the talking!)
- Discuss specific topics or projects that they might have in mind (and funding) for potential PhD students.

Example questions to ask:

It's a good idea to write your questions out ahead of time and have them in front of you.

- How large is the lab group currently?
- How long does it usually take your students to finish their program?
- How many graduate students have you advised? How many graduate students are you currently advising?
- What are some examples of careers/jobs recent graduate students in your lab have gone on to do?
- Do your students work on your projects? Or design their own?
- How does funding work for graduate students in your lab? Do you have space on your current grants or do you expect students to acquire their own research grants?
- What is the lab structure? How collaborative are lab projects?
- Describe your advising style - is it more hands-off or hands-on?
- How often do you meet with students?
- *[if you are interested in this]* Would you be willing to act as a co-advisor?
- What kind of outreach/diversity/inclusion initiatives does your lab participate in?
- Do you have any suggestions or tips for my application?
- Which department should I apply through?
 - Often faculty advise in multiple departments - funding and experience can differ drastically between departments! They may know about additional funding opportunities.
- Do you know of any grants or fellowships at the university that I would be eligible for?
- Can I get the contact information of other grad students or post-docs in the lab?

Ask them about lab culture and expectations:

- How cohesive is the lab? How is the lab culture?
- Do students work long hours?
- How often do students get time off?
- How communal is lab space/project work?
- How would you describe the advisor's mentoring style?
- What is the reputation of the advisor on campus?
- Do you have any advice for me?

Note: If your potential advisor won't give you this contact information - RUN!

Finalize written statements

- Be sure to personalize a section of each statement to each program. Explain why THIS school is the best fit for you and your scientific career.

Tip: Try to make this section as unique to each school as possible - it is helpful to identify specific programs or facilities that you will benefit from. For example, a field station is great to mention if you wanted to do field work.

- Be sure to directly name potential advisors in your personal statement. Make it extremely clear that you have talked with potential advisors! This is often how they identify who to bring in for interviews.

Check in with letter of recommendation writers

It can be helpful to check-in with your letter writers as you get close to submitting your applications. Check in with them 1-2 weeks before the deadline, and 1-2 days before the final deadline to make sure the letter is on their radar.

- You can submit your application prior to all the letters being received.
- Even if the letter is not submitted a few hours before the deadline, as long as you have touched-base with your letter writer, they will very likely submit it (many academics have a bad habit of submitting right at deadlines)

Submit program applications

Most will consist of main/background information (similar to undergraduate applications), personal info, personal statement, research statement, diversity/additional statements, and letters of recommendation. It is helpful to submit these a few days before the application deadline just in case anything goes wrong or the website crashes.

- Double check that each application/essay is going to the correct school!

Tip: Create a folder for each program where you save the materials that you've tailored to that program with a descriptive name (e.g., UMN_application -> "UMN_personal_statement.doc")

- Application fees can range from \$50 - \$100 to submit - this can add up!
 - Most programs offer a fee waiver (it NEVER hurts to ask/email!). Requesting a fee waiver from your program will NOT impact your chances of getting accepted. The worst they can say is no!
 - If you need financial assistance and fee waivers are not available via the program you are applying to, you can also seek out assistance from FAFSA (see the [GRE section](#)) - Give yourself some extra time with this, it can be slow!
- Celebrate! Take a break and do something for yourself :)

SPRING

February - April

Check in with potential advisors

It is good practice to keep in touch with potential advisors that you are excited about. Touch base again once you have heard back about interviews or admission.

- You can also ask them about the status of your application - sometimes they will have information on where the committee is at in the process!
- Update them on your research and ask about funding and projects they have going on.

Interview Weekend

Programs interested in you will invite you and a group of potential admittees to an interview round (usually in person) sometime in January-February.

- Travel costs: In person interviews will be paid for - you should NOT be covering your own travel expenses (flights/gas, housing, & most of the food should be organized for you and completely covered by the department).
 - **Note:** International students (or those located abroad during the application period) likely will not have their travel/flights covered. These students are set up with zoom interviews.
- These visits act as time for the program to evaluate your fit AND for you to evaluate the program. They will attempt to recruit you along with interviewing you!
 - This is also a great opportunity to meet you potential classmates/cohort
 - Even if you think you likely will not choose a school - still attend the interview! It is one of the best ways to get a sense of the program, advisor, campus, and city - you might be surprised at how your rankings change post-interview!
- This is NOT a time to over-indulge on free alcohol and party. Though you may not be with faculty the entire weekend, you are being “informally interviewed” by grad-students and others in the program - even off campus or at social events. Have fun, be social, but make good decisions (behavior matters!)
- Though stressful, they also can be fun! Expect a lot of good food. For more on what to expect, see box 5

Box 5: Rock the Interview Weekend

The interview will usually take place over the course of 2-4 days. Programs will pay for your travel costs and put you up in either a hotel or a homestay with a current graduate student.

The main part of the interview will consist of you meeting with faculty. You will meet with 3-10 faculty you listed on your application as well as your potential advisor in 15-60 minute blocks of time. Additionally, you may have an interview with an admission committee or graduate program coordinator. Outside of school hours, often you will spend time with current graduate students or potential lab members on field trips or at dinners. You will usually get some time with graduate students away from faculty - be sure to ask them questions too!

Use this time to ask a TON of questions. This is a chance for you to decide how well you fit into this program. Bring a notebook and take notes (it's not weird). Topics to ask about:

Program Staff/Graduate Admissions:

- Class/course requirements
- Teaching requirements
- Qualification exam process
- Funding availability/duration
- Summer funding and expectations
- University facilities and resources available to grad-students
 - Are there opportunities for career training/development outside of academia?
- Are there opportunities for childcare and family housing?
- Additional fees (student and international student fees)

Tip: Ask about student fees: there is often a semester fee for students taking classes. How does this compare to the stipend?

Current Grad Students:

- Classes/qualification exams
- Funding availability
- Culture/climate of the department (positive AND negative)
- Social life/climate of the graduate students (positive AND negative)
- Time to graduation
- How they like the city/university
 - Cost of living compared to living stipend
 - Transportation to and from school
 - Neighborhoods and locations to live
- General happiness in the program (any regrets or advice?)
- Reputation of your potential advisor

Faculty (outside of your potential advisor):

- Skim the bios/websites/papers of each faculty you will meet with (you should get your schedule ahead of time)
- Ask about their research and collaborations
 - What facilities do they utilize on campus?
- Share projects/experiences you have had that motivated you to apply for a PhD
- Talk about your research you are excited about working on both short and long term.
- Ask what they think are the strengths and weaknesses of the program/university

Potential Advisor:

While school, program, and university facilities are important - the number one most important factor in your grad-school career, success, and mental health will be your advisor. These in-person meetings are hugely helpful in deciding on an advisor and lab for a very formative and influential time in your scientific career. Think really critically about how well your styles and personalities mesh. Do not ignore red-flags at this stage!

- Talk about research! This should be exciting!
- Check out research space: lab space and potentially field sites.
- This is the time to see if you 'click' with this person! They will have a major influence on your future career so you want to make sure it is a good fit.
 - Do you like them?
 - Do you see yourself working with them for 5-6 years
 - Do your advisor/advisee styles seem to mesh?
 - Do they seem excited about you and your work?
 - Does it seem like mentoring graduate students is important to them?

Tip: This is also a good time to reach out/meet with potential lab members to get additional perspectives on an advisor's mentoring style (see box 4).

Questions YOU should be prepared to answer:

- Tell me about yourself...
- Why are you interested in this field?
- Why are you interested in this school and how do you think you will fit into this program?
- What are you looking for/expect to gain from a graduate program?
- What are your major research interests?
- What are your career goals?
- What questions do you have for me? (see above -- you are super prepared!)

After the interview:

It's possible you could have multiple interview weekends back-to-back. Though the first thing you may want to do when the visit is over is curl up and sleep, take a few minutes to consolidate your thoughts and impressions of the weekend. Make a quick list of pros and cons or jot down anything that stuck out to you about your potential advisor, the program, university, or city. This will make it easier to keep all the schools from blending together later when you have to make a decision.

Admission Results

Offer letters will typically start to come out in late February/early March (see box 6). Don't worry if you don't get one immediately - each admission cycle and school are very different. Offer letters will contain a funding package: this should include tuition waiver, healthcare, and a living stipend guaranteed for 4-5 years.

- Feel free to reach out to your potential advisor or program admissions director to ask about status if you have not heard back by mid-late March.
- No decision on your end needs to be made until April 15th (this is true of all schools) - no need to rush! Wait until you hear back from everyone before making a decision.
- Research your funding package offer. Compare your stipend offer to the ones listed [here](#). Be sure you are taking into account summer funding as sometimes schools list funding as one 12-month amount or broken into 9-month and 3-month chunks .
 - Keep in mind that schools can offer other benefits beyond just the stipend: extensive healthcare, relocation stipend, subsidized housing, child care, technology fund, fellowship funding without a teaching requirement, etc. . . .
- Consider whether you are in a position to negotiate for a better offer. You can sometimes get additional funding by explaining that you received a better offer elsewhere or that financial considerations are weighing on your decision - see more [here](#).
 - Think critically about your financial constraints. Do you have a partner or family? Will they need to relocate? Do you need to cover the cost of childcare? Are you an international student that will have travel, visa, and relocation expenses? These are all valid reasons to support a negotiation for a higher stipend.

Box 6: If you are not accepted

DO NOT BE DISCOURAGED. Grad school is hard to get into. Funding is low and often **unsuccessful applications are not indicative of your potential as a student** - decisions can be pretty random and “post-pandemic” the number of applicants has [greatly increased](#).

If you are not accepted - give yourself some time to mope but also be proud of all the work you have put in this year. Try reaching out to the department or your potential advisor for advice on how to make your application stronger - many will be willing to give you feedback or even want you to apply again next round. If grades or research experience was holding you back, consider trying out a masters program before starting your PhD (some programs even offer combined degrees!) You’ve already gone through the process once, it will be much easier the second time. Listen to what your potential advisors and mentors suggest and spend the next year gaining more experience.

Try not to stress. If you really want to pursue a career in research, you will find a way!!

Select final program (April 15th)

Don’t rush it! Talk it through to the important people in your life (family, partners, friends, etc..) and your mentors/research advisors!

- Try making a pro-con list. - things to think about:
 - Course requirements
 - Funding and benefits + livability
 - Advisor fit (do you like them AND their research?)
 - Research money and university resources
 - Career development resources
 - General grad student happiness
 - Location of school - can you pursue your hobbies?
- Remember: ultimately, this is just school!! You can always switch advisors, change programs, or even transfer schools. This decision is not the end-all-be-all. Try not to stress too much :)

Once you have made a decision you should send follow-up emails with those advisors you did not select. This is a great way to maintain your network as you may collaborate or work with them in the future.

- Consider sending updates and thank-you emails to your letter writers and those that helped you out with your apps. They will want to hear about your decision!

CELEBRATE!! You did it! Congrats on all the hard work :)

GLOSSARY/COMMON ACRONYMS

* indicates a term found elsewhere in the glossary

Academia: Refers to the community and careers that focus on research, higher-education, and scholarship. Typically these are jobs based heavily in research and teaching at academic institutions and universities (think professor, research scientist/technician, graduate student). Often discussed or used in contrast with government or industry* jobs and positions.

Adjunct: A professor who teaches & lectures on a limited or restricted contract (hired on a semester, or single academic year basis). They are not eligible for tenure* and thus have the potential to switch to other schools or industry* positions. Compare with Assistant Professor*, Associate Professor,* or Full Professor*

Admissions Committee: A group of 3-4 professors in the department that will review complete applications for a graduate program. This committee is typically lead by the DGA* and this group will create a “long-short-list” of applicants who they will consider for admission. Every department and program will differ in how they evaluate candidates but many will look at application components (statements and letters) combined with feedback from other professors in the department (i.e. if you have reached out to a professor, they may request the committee consider you for an interview).

Advisory Committee/Chair: A group of 4-5 professors that will help advise you on your progress through graduate school and your overall research/dissertation*. This committee will also conduct and evaluate your preliminary/qualification exams* as well as your final dissertation defense.* This committee is selected by the graduate student typically in their first year of study and usually made up of individuals with differing expertise that can advise on various aspects of one's research. A committee will be led by a “chair” or “head” which is typically your primary advisor (the professor whose lab you are in).

Applied Research/Science: A term loosely used to describe research that is designed to solve a specific problem or answer a very practical/specific question. Applied research is typically very solutions based and focuses on how to adapt and apply the pre-existing base of scientific knowledge to real-life situations. In EEB* This term is usually used to refer to work conducted in conjunction with conservation groups, government agencies, farmers, and more. Often used in contrast with basic science*

Assistantship/Appointment: A form of financial aid for graduate students to be paid in exchange for their work. Appointments typically come with a tuition waiver* as well as a living stipend*. Common appointments are TAs*, RAs*, and GA*s.

Assistant Professor: A professor in the first position of the tenure* track job. A typical progression through the tenure sequence is assistant -> associate* -> full professor*. Assistant professors are typically early-career professors. This is likely their first faculty role at this institution and they will be focused on developing their lab and research program, along with recruiting graduate students and postdocs*.

Associate Professor: A professor who has received a promotion after starting at the university in a faculty* position - they may have already received or will be working towards receiving tenure*. A typical progression through the tenure sequence is assistant* -> associate -> full professor*. Associate professors are likely to have productive and established labs along with postdocs and graduate students.

Basic Research/Science: Basic research is a term loosely used to describe research that tries to expand the already existing scientific knowledge base. The main motivation of basic research is to expand human knowledge and focuses heavily on theory and “laws” of nature. Many view basic science as laying down the foundation for the applied science* to draw from.

Candidacy: A title awarded to graduate students that have completed their coursework and passed their qualifications/preliminary exams* but have not yet completed a dissertation. You may see titles written out as “PhD Candidate”

Chapter: Subsection of a dissertation*. Typically, each chapter represents one project or dataset collected by a graduate student. You may hear graduate students refer to working on specific chapters (“second chapter”) meaning they are developing a specific aspect of their overall dissertation.

Co-Advisor: While some graduate student have one main advisor, other projects/students might benefit from two different expertises beyond just their advisory committee*. These can be two professors in the same department (ex: a plant ecologist and a soil ecologist), but more frequently they are professors from two different fields that the graduate student will combine in their dissertation* project (ex: a tree ecologist and an environmental policy professor). Students with 2 main advisors are referred to as the student’s “Co-Advisors”.

Cohort: A group of graduate students that begin and move through a graduate program together. Some programs explicitly advertise and build a cohort environment - often these students will take similar courses their first 1-2 years in the program.

COGS: Council of Graduate Students. A governing body of graduate students that act as liaisons between the graduate students at a university and the administration. Typically you have very small dues incorporated into your student fee* and each graduate program can elect one voting member. COGSs lobbies for grad-student worker rights and benefits, as well as supporting student professional development and research. Recently, some programs have [unionized](#) their councils!

CV: Curriculum Vitae - a specific type of academic resume. This document covers all of your major academic milestones such as research experiences, teaching, publications, awards, and more. See our [section above](#) on compiling a CV!

Dean: The head of a college that makes big-picture administrative decisions such as budgeting, funding, and hiring of faculty. The Dean is typically an experienced tenured* professor who has given up most teaching and research.

Defense: An oral examination that is the final exam for a graduate student on which completion awards a PhD (or MA/MS). At a defense, a graduate student explains their research/dissertation* and “defends” or answers questions from their advisory committee* and the department on the accuracy and significance of their research, findings, and conclusions. Some programs will additionally have a defense of a thesis or dissertation proposal as part of the qualifying/preliminary exams*.

Dissertation: A major body of original research which makes a contribution to the current scientific knowledge or field. The written dissertation acceptance and defense* marks the end and awarding of a PhD*. Typically dissertations are broken into chapters*, each representing a major project conducted while in the program.

DGA: Director of Graduate Admissions. The professor responsible for overseeing the graduate admission process for a particular program. They will assemble and head the admissions committee* as well as act as a point of contact for prospective students.

DGS: Director of Graduate Studies. The professor responsible for overseeing the graduate program. The DGS will function as an advisor to guide and communicate directly with current graduate students on their course of study, research, and schedule. They also act as the liaison between the students in the department and the dean*.

EEB or EEPB: Acronym for ecology based departments and graduate programs. Ecology, Evolution, and Behavior (EEB), or Ecology, Evolution, and Population Biology (EEPB), or some combination of these letters. Sometimes departments will also include ‘Conservation Biology’

Faculty: All employees who hold the rank of ‘instructor’ or higher in an academic institution or University. This includes lecturers, teaching staff, course administrators, as well as adjuncts* and professors.

FAFSA: Free Application for Federal Student Aid. A federal need-based student financial aid.

Fee Waiver: A graduate program may cover or drop the fees associated with submitting an application to their graduate program. Email the program contact to inquire about fee waivers including any potential financial limitations. It never hurts to ask!

Fellowship: Money that is given or awarded to a graduate student. Typically fellowships cover a tuition waiver* and living stipends* resulting in the student not needing to take on an additional appointment* for compensation. Fellowships can be external (government and private groups) or internal to the University. Students can apply to various fellows prior to starting in a program, and throughout the course of their program. See our [section above](#) for examples and more information on applying.

Full Professor (or just Professor): A professor who has received tenure* and reached the highest promotion available. A typical progression through the tenure sequence is assistant* -> associate* -> full professor. Many universities have both time and productivity requirements to be eligible for promotion to full professor. Advisors with these titles are typically running well-established and productive labs, and have made significant contributions in their field,

their institution, and in teaching. They also are likely to have mentored multiple graduate students to completion of PhDs. Full professors may take on additional more senior-leadership roles in the department or college, see DGS* or DGA*.

GA: Graduate Assistant. A type of appointment* awarded to graduate students. Differing from TA* and RA* appointments, GA typically are involved with tasks outside of research and teaching (though this will vary at every institution). A common example of a GA appointment in EEB* is the maintenance of a specimen or museum collection .

Grant: Money to support research related endeavors, expenses, and travel. These are awarded to a particular scientist/group of scientists/lab explicitly to support research-related costs (though this can vary). Compare with fellowship*.

GRE: Graduate Record Exam - the standardized test for entrance into many graduate programs. The GRE [does not predict graduate school success](#) and [disenfranchises students from low-income backgrounds and people of color/members of under-represented groups](#). Thus, MANY programs are [dropping](#) the requirement . See our suggestions [above](#)!

Industry: A term that loosely refers to scientific jobs/careers outside of academia*. These may be in corporate/commercial settings, or other government, non-profit, or consulting positions.

LOR - Letters of Recommendation. Typically written by faculty/research advisors in support of your graduate school applications, internships, jobs, and more.

MS or MSci: Masters of Science. A 2-3 year graduate school program focused on course work and development of a thesis*. Masters programs typically prepare you for industry, government, and teaching jobs. Though not required, MS can provide directed research experience in preparation for a PhD.

NSF or NSF-GRFP: [National Science Foundation](#) - a government organization that provides many of the grants and research money supporting basic research.* One popular and competitive graduate-student fellowship* that NSF provides is the Graduate Research Fellowship Program ([GRFP](#)). See more in box 3!

Outreach: A term used to describe activities and service led by research institutes, universities, departments, or smaller lab/student groups. Typically outreach events are aimed at promoting public awareness of science and contributing to public interest and scientific education. These events can be targeted at sharing science with education/schools, the general public, or government/policy makers. These activities can range from larger institutions (like a museum) or small one-time events (hosting a booth at a farmers market).

PhD: Doctorate of Philosophy. The highest degree level awarded in higher education. A PhD is distinguished by the production a dissertation* that contributes new knowledge to a particular research topic. PhDs are required for many teaching and research positions at universities and in academia* but are also utilized in many industry* positions.

PI/Principal Investigator: The head of a laboratory or leader of a research group or grant* PIs are active in research with potential to fund PhD students or post-docs*

Post-Doc: ‘Post-doc’toral fellowship - a 1-3 year position for individuals who have finished their PhD and wish to continue working in academia. Postdocs typically conduct research and teach to prepare/bolser their CV* in preparation for applying to very competitive assistant professor* positions.

Preliminary/Comprehensive/Qualification Exams (Quals): A set of written and oral exams given to a graduate student typically 2-3 years into the program after they have completed their coursework. The goal of these exams is to test student knowledge of the field and determine if they are “qualified”/ready to complete a dissertation* Exams vary widely between programs and fields but some common forms include a combination of written knowledge tests, written dissertation* proposals, oral proposal defenses*, and oral knowledge exams. Students that do not pass their exams often have the option to complete a MS* or masters degree (though this will vary by program and student). Upon passing all components, the student earns the title of PhD Candidate* and often a stipend* increase :)

R1: A ranking scale used to classify doctoral (PhD*) granting-institutions that conduct research. R1 is the highest classification and identifies universities that have “very high” research activity and access to facilities. Often “R1” universities are places that have strong doctoral programs, facilities, and resources.

RA: Research Assistant - A type of graduate student appointment* . Students with RAs typically work part-time in a research lab and are hired/supported by a specific faculty member in exchange for compensation (see assistantship*) RA positions are typically funded by outside institutions and grants*. Compare with GA* and TA*

REU: Research Experience for Undergraduates - a summer internships experience that heavily involves independent research. The program is hosted by NSF* and provides great experience in preparation for graduate school. More info [here](#).

Rotations: Or ‘laboratory rotations’ can be part of the first-year of graduate school in some programs. Students conduct small pilot projects for 2-3 months and will ‘rotate’ through 3-4 different laboratories/Pis* before selecting their advisor. Rotations in conjunction with coursework helps expose students to a broad array of research topics and labs available in their program. Rotations are in contrast to programs where students pre-select their advisor as part of their application. You will still need to [contact potential advisors](#) prior to applying to programs with rotations.

Service: A term used in academia to describe activities that do not directly relate to teaching and research requirements of a position but benefit the university/department/program (in contrast to the public in outreach*). Example service positions are sitting on application committees, advising committees at the University level, or organizing an event/conference.

SOP - Statement of Purpose - a written statement commonly part of an application to a graduate program and fellowships. Requirements will vary by program but generally these statements cover research experiences and future career goals.

Stipend: Or 'living stipend' - an amount of money given to PhD/students for living expenses (outside of tuition) in exchange for an appointment (see assistantship*, TA*, RA*, or GA*). Fellowships* provide a student with a stipend without the teaching/research requirements associated with other appointments. .

Student Fees: A fee associated with costs of being a student at a University. This fee helps to cover services like COGS*, campus transportation, University Records Office, Career Centers, student groups etc... Graduate students are required to pay these fees each semester out of pocket – they are typically NOT covered by your department/tuition. These fees can range wildly between universities - be sure to inquire about them at an interview to see how they compare with the stipend*

TA: Teaching Assistant. A type of appointment* awarded to graduate students. Teaching assistantships are very common among graduate students and often required by graduate programs. A TA will work under a professor to help facilitate and run an undergraduate course. This may involve lecturing, running discussion or lab sections, grading, and giving exams.

Tenure/Tenure Track: Tenure is a status given to professors at academic institutions. Academic tenure means a professor has been granted lifetime employment with the institution and protects them from being fired without cause. Tenure status positions are highly competitive and the promotion process usually takes 5-7 years (see associate* and full* professor). Though tenure marks the top of the academic promotions, additional senior titles can be given to tenured employees (Endowed Professor, Distinguished Professor, Professor Emeritus, etc . . .). Professors with tenure titles are not likely to change institutions.

TOEFL - Test of English as a Foreign Language. A test commonly required of international student applications to graduate programs in the United States. The test evaluates proficiency in reading, listening comprehension, and writing in English. See more [here](#).

Tuition Waiver: A term that refers to the cost of tuition being covered by a student's appointment/assistantship*. The university will charge a tuition fee which the department will then cover for you. This exchange is sometimes referred to as a "tuition waiver"

REFERENCES

Clark, Adam (2018). *The graduate school cookbook: One way to approach PhD applications in ecology*. University of Minnesota EEB. [Link](#) and [github](#).

Doyle, Alison (2022). *The difference between a Resume and a Curriculum Vitae*. The balance online publication. [Link](#)

Doyle, Alison (2021) *How to write a Curriculum Vitae (CV)*. The balance online publication. [Link](#)

German Lab (Donovan German, UC Irvine EEB) *A guide for applying to graduate school in biology*. [Link](#)

Gill, Jacquelyn. (2013) *So, you want to go to grad school? Nail the inquiry email*. The Contemplative Mammoth blog. [Link](#).

Johnson, Vicki (2021) *How to negotiate your funding offer for graduate school: an email template*. ProFellow Online. [Link](#).

FIELD GUIDE RESOURCES

- Field Guides seminar “Graduate School 101” ([slides](#))
- [GRE prep, practice tests, and other resources](#)
- [Suggested things to do in your undergraduate as preparation for grad-school](#)
- [External funding opportunities for graduate/professional school](#)
- Field Guides ‘[Guide to finding summer research internships](#)’

And so much more! Check out our full resource archive on our [website](#).

ADDITIONAL GUIDES

- UC Davis EEB Grad Preview: an awesome website chock full of resources, seminars and guides compiled by grad-students! [Link](#)
- The Graduate School Cookbook: One way to approach PhD applications in ecology. University of Minnesota EEB by Adam Clark (2018). [Link](#).

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